

The Structure and Stereochemistry of Entagenic Acid

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The structure of entagenic acid, a new triterpene acid sapogenin from the kernel of the seeds of *Entada phaseoloides* Merrill, has now been confirmed as 3 β ,15 α ,16 α -trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-28-oic acid (IIa). The experiments leading to this structure are presented.

THE isolation of a new triterpene acid sapogenin, entagenic acid from the kernel of the seeds of *Entada phaseoloides* Merrill (Syn. *E. scandens*, *E. pursaetha*) was reported from this laboratory and its structure was proposed as 3 β ,21 α ,22 α -trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-28-oic acid¹⁻³ (I). Later, Wen Chin *et al*⁴ isolated a glycoside of entagenic acid from the same source and this has been shown to have significant antitumor activity against 256 carcinosarcoma in rats. Later, Barua *et al*^{5,6} revised the structure of entagenic acid as 3 β ,15 α ,16 α -trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-28-oic acid (IIa) and this paper details the experiments leading to the revised structure.

Entagenic acid on heating with pyridine and acetic anhydride on steam bath yielded a product which showed two distinct spots in tlc. One of these spots corresponded to that of the amorphous triacetyl entagenic acid reported earlier^{2,3}. The above acetate mixture on treatment with diazomethane furnished triacetyl methyl entagenate (IIc), C₃₇H₅₆O₈, m.p. 203-205° and diacetyl methyl entagenate (IIe), C₃₅H₅₄O₇, m.p. 200° (softens at 175°). Methyl entagenate (IIb) when treated with pyridine and acetic anhydride at 0° furnished mainly diacetyl methyl entagenate (IIe) and 3-acetyl methyl entagenate (IIe), C₃₅H₅₂O₆, m.p. 262-65° and only a trace of triacetyl methyl entagenate. The above experiments clearly showed that one of the hydroxyl groups of the α -glycol system in entagenic acid is hindered.

The α -glycol system in entagenic acid was shown earlier to be *cis* as it easily formed an acetonide and consumed lead tetraacetate at a fast rate. So if the α -glycol system is located in ring E, the configurations of these two hydroxyl groups should be either 21 β ,22 β or 21 α ,22 α . Entagenic acid did not form any 28 \rightarrow 21 lactone like machaerinic acid^{2,3} which has a 21 β -hydroxyl group and hence the configuration of the α -glycol system should be 21 α ,22 α if it is located in ring E. But the 21 α and 22 α hydroxyl groups both undergo acetylation with pyridine and acetic anhydride under mild conditions^{7,8}. Therefore, the alternative positions (C-15 and C-16) for the α -glycol system had to be considered. Now, if the α -glycol system is located

in ring D then there are two possible configurations for the two hydroxyl groups, either 15 β ,16 β or 15 α ,16 α . 15 β hydroxyl group is known to undergo easy lactonization with 28-carboxyl group (cf. dumortierigenin⁹ and proceragenin¹⁰) but entagenic acid did not form such a lactone. Hence, if the α -glycol system is located in ring D then the configurations of these hydroxyl groups must be 15 α (equatorial) and 16 α (axial). The 16 α (axial)-hydroxyl group in an oleanene skeleton is known to be highly hindered (cf. echinocystic acid¹¹ and barringtogenol C¹²) and this explains the hindrance of one of the hydroxyl groups of the α -glycol system in entagenic acid. The hydroxyl group at C-3 was earlier shown to be β (equatorial). On the basis of the above discussions entagenic acid should be 3 β ,15 α ,16 α -trihydroxy-olean-12-en-28-oic acid (IIa). This conclusion was further supported by the facts presented below. The diacetyl methyl entagenate (IIa) is considered to be a 3,15-diacetate because preferential acetylation of the 15 α (equatorial)-hydroxyl group rather than the 16 α (axial)-hydroxyl group is expected. That it was so was evident from its nmr spectrum (CDCl₃, 60 MHz). The two acetoxy groups (-O-CO-CH₃) appeared as sharp singlets at 2.03 (3H) and 2.07 (3H) δ . A three proton singlet at 3.68 δ was due to the 28-carbomethoxy group (-COOCH₃). The C-12 vinyl proton appeared as a broad multiplet at 5.5 δ . The signal for the H-15 appeared at 5.15 δ (d, J=4 Hz), and H-16 at 4.44 δ (d, J=4Hz) which was partly overlapped by the signal at 4.48 δ (1H, m) due to 3-H. If the diacetate was a 3,16-diacetate, the signal for the H-16 would have appeared further downfield than 5.69 δ (observed for the 16-H in case of diacetyl methyl echinocystate) because the presence of vicinal hydroxyl group at C-15 would cause further downfield shift of the signal. So the diacetate is a 3,15-diacetate (IIa). This was further supported by the nmr spectrum (CDCl₃, 60 MHz) of the triacetyl entagenic acid (IIa) which showed the signal at the expected low field (5.81 δ , 1H, d, J=4 Hz) for the 16-H and at 5.3 δ (1H, d, J=4 Hz) for the 15-H. Besides these, there were three sharp singlets at 1.92 (3H), 2.01 (3H) and 2.1 (3H) δ for the three acetoxy groups, a triplet at

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4.52 δ (1H, $J=8$ Hz) for the 3-H and a multiplet at 5.5 δ for the C-12 vinyl proton.

LAH reduction of methyl entagenate gave a tetrol (IIIa), $C_{28}H_{50}O_4$, m.p. 254-56°, and this on heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam bath furnished a mixture of acetates from which tetrol tetra-acetate (IIIb), $C_{28}H_{50}O_8$, m.p. 123-27° could be isolated in pure state by column chromatography. Its nmr spectrum ($CDCl_3$, 60 MHz) was in good agreement with its proposed structure (IIIb). The signals assignable to 23-, 24- (s, 6H, 0.87 δ), 25-, 29- (s, 6H, 0.93 δ) and 30- (s, 3H, 0.97 δ) methyl groups appeared at the region as observed in case of 3 β -acetoxy compounds of the Δ^{12} -oleanene series¹³ but those for the 26- (s, 3H, 1.0 δ) and 27- (s, 3H, 1.4 δ) methyl groups appeared at lower field due to the vicinity of the acetoxy groups at C-15 and C-16 positions. The signals for the four acetoxy groups ($-O-COCH_3$) appeared as sharp singlets at 1.93 (3H), 2.04 (3H) and 2.13 (6H) δ . The methylene protons of the 28-primary acetoxy group ($-CH_2O-CO-CH_3$) appeared as AB pattern centred at 3.64 (d, $J=11.5$ Hz) and 4.09 (d, $J=11.5$ Hz) δ .

The signals for the H-3 appeared as a broad triplet at 4.5 δ and the signals for the 15 β -H and 16 β -H appeared as an AB type centred at 5.24 (d, $J=4$ Hz) and 5.45 (d, $J=4$ Hz) δ , respectively. The low coupling constant (4 Hz) indicated *cis* relationship between the above two protons which necessitates *cis*-orientation for the α -glycol system in IIIb and consequently in entagenic acid. The 12-H signal appears at 5.49 δ (1H, m). It was thought that if the diacetate was a 3,15-diacetate (IIa) then on dehydration by treatment with $POCl_3$ in pyridine, it would lead to the formation of a 15-keto compound (IV). With this objective the above reaction was carried out. On working up, a major product $C_{28}H_{50}O_8$, (M^+ 526), m.p. 192°, and another product in trace, $C_{28}H_{50}O_8$, (M^+ 526), m.p. 203°, were obtained. The mass spectral fragmentation pattern

- a, $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$
 b, $R_1=R_2=R_3=H$; $R_4=CH_3$
 c, $R_1=R_2=R_3=Ac$; $R_4=OH$
 d, $R_1=R_2=Ac$; $R_3=H$; $R_4=OH$
 e, $R_1=Ac$; $R_2=R_3=H$; $R_4=CH_3$
 f, $R_1=R_2=R_3=Ac$; $R_4=H$

- a, $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=H$
 b, $R_1=R_2=R_3=R_4=Ac$

Scheme 1

(Scheme 1) of the former is typical of a 15-keto compound¹⁴ and hence the structure of the compound must be IV. If the keto group was not at 15 then instead of a peak at m/e 277 a peak at m/e 276 would have been observed due to normal r.D.A. fragmentation. IR spectrum of IV showed bands at 1750, 1735 and 1725 cm^{-1} for the acetoxy, carbomethoxyl and the keto groups, respectively.

The formation of the 15-keto compound (IV) clearly locates the α -glycol system in entagenic acid at 15,16-positions. This also supports the earlier stereochemical assignment of the α -glycol system in entagenic acid.

The second product was characterized as 3-acetyl-16-keto methyl olean-12-ene-28-oate by direct comparison of m.p. and ir spectra with an authentic sample prepared by oxidation of 3-acetyl methyl echinocystate available in the laboratory. The formation of the 16-keto compound, though in traces, is rather interesting. There are two alternative explanations: (i) the diacetate described earlier may contain the 3,15-diacetate and trace of 3,16-diacetate formed by acyl migration during column chromatography, for such acyl migrations are known to occur^{15,16}, (ii) the acyl migration takes place during the process of dehydration. The second process looks more probable as the diacetate showed single spot in tlc over silica gel G and also over $AgNO_3$ -impregnated silica gel G plates in various solvent systems. It may be mentioned here that the 15 α -(equatorial)-OH group undergoes easy dehydra-

tion to give 15,16-double bond whereas the dehydration of 15 β (axial)-OH group leads to rearranged product (cf. dumortierigenin⁶).

The data presented above conclusively establishes the structure and stereochemistry of entagenic acid as 3 β ,15 α ,16 α -trihydroxy-olean-12-ene-28-oic acid (IIa).

Experimental

All melting points reported were recorded in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Petroleum ether refers to the fraction b.p. 60-80°.

Acetylation of entagenic acid: Entagenic acid (1.2 g) was heated for 1.5 hr on steam bath with pyridine (10 ml) and acetic anhydride (15 ml) and it was worked up in the usual way. TLC showed two distinct spots, one of which corresponded to an authentic sample of entagenic acid triacetate.

The above acetate mixture (1 g) was esterified with ethereal diazomethane. It was then worked up in the usual way. TLC showed two distinct spots. The mixture was resolved by column chromatography over silica gel. The benzene-chloroform (3:1, v/v) eluate gave a fraction which crystallized from aqueous ethanol, m.p. 203-5° (410 mg) (tri-acetyl methyl entagenate, IIc). (Found: C, 70.81; H, 8.76; M⁺ 628. C₃₇H₅₆O₈ requires C, 70.67; H, 8.98%; Mol. wt. 628). Further elution of the column with benzene-chloroform (2:1) gave a fraction which crystallized from chloroform-pet. ether, m.p. 200° (softens at 175°) (425 mg), (diacetyl methyl entagenate, II d). (Found: C, 71.22; H, 9.55; M⁺ 586. C₃₅H₅₄O₇ requires C, 71.64; H, 9.28%; Mol. wt. 586).

Acetylation of methyl entagenate at 0°: Methyl entagenate (1.5 g) was treated with pyridine (15 ml) and acetic anhydride (18 ml) and kept overnight at 0°. It was worked up in the usual way. The product showed two major spots in tlc and a faint spot which correspond to the triacetyl methyl entagenate. Column chromatography over silica gel gave triacetyl methyl entagenate (50 mg), diacetyl methyl entagenate (525 mg) and another fraction which crystallized from methanol, m.p. 262-65° (290 mg) (3-acetyl methyl entagenate). (Found: M⁺ 544. C₃₃H₅₂O₆ requires Mol. wt. 544).

Lithium aluminium hydride reduction of methyl entagenate: A slurry of LAH (3 g) in dry ether (300 ml) was refluxed with a solution of methyl entagenate (750 mg) in ether for 8 hr. Working up in the usual way and repeated crystallization of the product from chloroform yielded the tetrol (IIIa), m.p. 254-56°. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 10.45. C₈₀H₅₀O₄ requires C, 75.9; H, 10.5%).

Acetylation of the tetrol: The tetrol (400 mg) was heated with pyridine (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (10 ml) on a steam bath for 5 hr. It was worked up in the usual way. It was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel G. The benzene-chloro-

form (5:1) eluate gave a fraction homogeneous in tlc. It could not be crystallized from any solvent. It was dissolved in minimum volume of chloroform and precipitated with pet. ether, m.p. 123-27° (tetrol tetra-acetate, IIIb). (Found: C, 70.82; H, 9.11. C₃₃H₅₀O₈ requires C, 71.00; H, 9.09%).

Treatment of diacetyl methyl entagenate with POCl₃: Diacetyl methyl entagenate (250 mg) was dissolved in dry pyridine (5 ml) and was cooled to below 0° in a freezing mixture. POCl₃ (8 ml) was then slowly added and left overnight. The mixture was then heated on steam bath for 3 hr. It was worked up in the usual way. It showed one major spot and one minor spot. It was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel when two fractions were obtained. The major fraction was crystallized from pet. ether, (IV), m.p. 192°. (Found: M⁺ 526. C₃₃H₅₀O₅ requires Mol. wt. 526).

The other fraction was crystallized from methanol, m.p. 203° (3-acetyl-16-keto methyl echinocystate). (Found: M⁺ 526. C₃₃H₅₀O₆ requires Mol. wt. 526).

Oxidation of 3-acetyl methyl echinocystate: 3-Acetyl methyl echinocystate (100 mg) was dissolved in pyridine (2 ml) and treated with CrO₃-pyridine complex in the usual way at 0°. Working up and crystallization of the product from methanol gave a product, m.p. 203° (3-acetyl-16-keto methyl echinocystate). (Found: M⁺ 526. C₃₃H₅₀O₆ requires Mol. wt. 526).

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